

PROCESSES IN THE STAGES OF CREATING A COORDINATE SCHEME OF THE PLACEMENT OF AN OPEN MINE

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Abstract: Ensuring proper development and production of mining enterprises is considered the main task of priority production. based on a scientifically based assessment of its geometric characteristics it is necessary to clearly understand the mineral deposit and the amount of the deposit, the location of the deposit, the area of the deposit. The main purpose of the research is the geological and geotechnological assessment of the mineral deposit, which provides the opening scheme and development of the deposit in the early period of the deposit. Calculations are carried out on the basis of geological analyzes necessary for the correct determination of the quantity and quality of reserves of the studied mine. The collection and processing of such material will be based on results that are sufficient for this technical formulation. It's open proper and economically feasible design processes for mine development are carried out. Research the methodology consists of determining and monitoring the coordinates of the extraction of underground resources and geometric modeling progressive and classic methods of geometric formation of mineral mass and rocks should be excavated in the right direction. It includes a set of measures aimed at initial collection and evaluation. Mining enterprises the most effective ways to solve the problem of geometrization of the area is to determine the location limit of the mineral. The obtained results allow, practical solution of mining problems related to reserve estimation shows mineral deposits, their genesis, nature of occurrence, quality, sorting possibilities. In mining based on which a set of effective methods has been developed on the statistical evaluation of mineral deposits, as well as the use of the latest geodata based on systems that provide high-quality and accurate calculation and evaluation mineral deposits consist of proper mining and proper placement of the parameters of the mine, which consists of drawing up a mine scheme.

Keywords: Open pit mining scheme, geology of the mine, mine location coordinates, mine parameters and geotechnological dimensions, geometric analysis

Introduction

In the mining of ore deposits, the quality and physical geometry (isotropy and anisotropy), properties and characteristics of the ore are of particular

importance. chemical properties of rocks and minerals, which are one of the most important tasks in mining ensures smooth and easy processes in the mining enterprise. The graphic-analytical method allows to establish the distribution of the coordinates of the location of the mining enterprise to create a spatial model of the deposit in order to determine its content and relationships allows determining the amount of mineral reserves differentially among components. Mine development requires large costs and their efficiency directly depends on the completeness and quality of information about deposits, mineral their composition depends on the availability of minerals and directly on mineral reserves. It's about processes problems can be solved on the basis of a set of studies aimed at geometric formation, statistical there are modern technologies and computer systems for the assessment of the deposit, modeling and monitoring of its shape, properties and volumes. Geometrical analysis of mining enterprises and underground modeling, geological location scheme, geochemical and other properties characterizing various properties of the mine and indicators of the mountain massif (structure, characteristics, condition) and georesource sources based on which they are geometrically modeled, including topographic surfaces and various types geotechnological boundary area is taken into account as forecasts. Geometrization is the methodological basis of subsurface geometry. The complex of geometrization methods consists in collecting and filling source data, geological mineralization systematization, pre-processing and accuracy assessment of data using variability based on the results obtained during prospecting, geodetic measurements, test studies, geophysical and special studies statistics, theory of random functions, calculus of finite differences will be necessary. Mathematical and geometrical dimensions of mining enterprises we will be able to determine based on modeling and model accuracy evaluation system. It is the use of the model to solve the research questions, as well as to determine the geological and geotechnological composition it is necessary to form a deposit. Parameters of mining enterprises in calculating the volume by the method of calculating heights calculate the size of the base mine boundary area, as well as the average mined height can be determined by In the calculation of mining and controlling the volumes between them the average value of the height is calculated over the entire area. Calculated the calculation of volumes by the method of vertical sections is used to calculate the volumes and the measured coordinates of the mine may be located. Geological prospecting and complex block figures of various types of objects with geodetic dimensions will have a complex profile of several different

layers, steps and sections. Their uniqueness In K-Mine in this way, the calculation of volumes and construction processes at the initial stage two triangulation surfaces for the new and old positions of the barrier that have as partitions it is necessary to draw a calculation contour. Triangulation surfaces are built based on the data of all objects included in each category and describes the appearance of a form consisting of layers. Then, the operation of their intersection is performed on the triangulation surfaces and with vertical planes, it makes it possible to determine the contours of the figures describing the sections. In the future, the solution of the problem is reduced to solving the standard problem of calculus and volumes can be connected to each other by the method of projections. So, a set of reporting documents will be formed in the settlement and all the necessary facilities (construction of departments and their numbering) is carried out. The article contains a calculation table with indicators calculation of the area for each section, as well as a graphical representation of each section in it are shown in the given scales.

Picture 1. The state of placement in the combined intervals of the calculation forms measured in the boundary area value of the mine.

Using these dimensions, create digital models of section surfaces, roof contours, and bases combined into two surfaces, roof surface and floor surface values are calculated. The marginal area of the mine does not include the area of off-balance sheet reserves. An empty block model is created and a geometric analysis is obtained in the obtained frame. The shape of the elementary block of the block model determined by the shape of the placer (thickness of the ore). In the coordinates of the location of the Tebin Bulak iron mine of the Republic of

Karakalpakstan a map of the location of the mine with low power relative to the distribution area is shown. According to available materials, none of the directions have a clear elongated shape in the plan. Therefore, the most coordinates are attached based on the optimal shape with the ratio of length, width and power $10 \times 10 \times 1$ m. Starting size the block of the block model is determined by taking into account two main factors. First, the geotechnological location of a single unit, which provides selective extraction from the selected mining technology, is attached based on the scale of the boundary area.

Picture 2. Coordinates and dimensions of the location scheme of the Tebin Bulak iron mine of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Conclusions

It is necessary to form a block model reflecting the distribution of the mine from the results obtained in the calculation of the location coordinates of the mine. It should be noted that the model allows not only more accurate assessment and reserves and other parameters of the mine, but also in order to make a decision on the fast direction, mining is carried out step by step depending on all the geological and geotechnological conditions in the mine or other factors. By capital mining processes assigning category contour indices to each of the blocks, all reserves of the block model divided into appropriate classes (categories). As a result of creating a report by block model, the distribution of reserves should be taken into account. The total amount of balance reserves Iron

in Tebin Bulak iron mine amounted to 2.5 thousand tons. In error inventory count was 7.5%. Solving a real scientific and technical problem geometric formation of the reserves of the mining enterprise aimed at ensuring the process shows mining production and design processes. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of Nukus Mining Institute, has many articles about mining enterprises and processes in mining enterprises. His interests are technological processes in mining enterprises, he is very interested in the layout of mines.

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